

Extended Data 1: Supplementary Information and Supplementary Figures

Research data management for bioimaging: the 2021 NFDI4BIOIMAGE community survey

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- Quality control and exclusion criteria
- Free-text comments
- Conditional survey logic
- Supplementary figures

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28 **Quality control and exclusion criteria**

29 **Data quality check protocol (refers to Extended Data 4 Analysis Sheet):**

30 1. Sheet 1: "RAW-priv-protect"

31 Raw data saved, unmanipulated, except question header formatted in a human-readable
32 fashion. All IP addresses were deleted to ensure privacy protection.

33 2. Sheet 2: "RAW marked for QC". RAW data marked for quality control checks, analysis
34 headers added (row 5 - 21), manual fields (pre-) analyzed and comments made

35 3. Deletion of all data that is non-compliant with quality control criteria:

36 *Complete dataset removal:*

37 3.1 Remove datasets that have failed both attention checks on page 4 and page 8

38 *applied 1 x (Entry # 226)*

39 *Partial data removal:*

40 3.2 Page 3: Remove data on pages 4 to 10, if the plausibility check was failed:

41 Q3.2-St-"no involvement in research" only plausibly if Q3.1-St = "research support" OR "no
42 involvement in research at all"

43 *not applicable, all entries passed*

44 3.3 Page 4: Remove entries up to incl. page 7, if attention check on page 4 is failed

45 *applied 5 x*

46 3.4 Page 8: Remove entries on pages 9-10, if "No, I/we do not perform any image
47 processing and analysis" is checked (failure in questionnaire logic detected)

48 *applied 7 x*

49 3.5 Page 11: Remove entries, if only one answer category is clicked continuously (non-
50 attentive clicking)

51 *applied 2 x*

52 3.6 Page 13: question "With respect to handling of bioimaging data in your research field:
53 What is your opinion about the following statements?": Remove entries, if only one answer
54 category is clicked continuously (non-attentive clicking)

55 *applied 4 x*

56 3.7 Page 15: Remove entries, if only one answer category is clicked continuously (non-
57 attentive clicking)

58 *not applicable*

59 3.8 Page 16: For each of the two questions: Remove entries of that question, if only one
60 category was clicked continuously (non-attentive clicking)

61 *Q16.1: applied 8 x*

62 *Q16.2: applied 4 x*

63 3.9 "What is your opinion on these statements about Data Management Plans (DMPs):" –

64 Delete statements 2 – 10, if the attention check was failed and the first question was
65 answered with “I fully agree” or “I partially agree”.

66 *applied 2 x*

67 4. Sheet 3: “QC-checked”: Data quality control finished, entries were marked with
68 „DELETED“ or „Not shown to this person“ – this serves as the basis for further analysis of
69 the subgroups

70 **Explanations of the exclusion criteria:**

71 (i) If 1st attention check is missed, then delete the data set until page 7.

72 *Explanation: The person was not attentive, which means we are not sure if he/she read the*
73 *instruction. Without reading instructions, the following answering options are not clear.*

74 (ii) If 2nd attention check is missed, there is no consequence.

75 *Explanation: no instructions which might be of importance are missed here.*

76 (iii) If 3rd attention check is missed,

77 (a) if the person knows what a DMP is (i.e. clicked I agree / I partially agree), delete all
78 answers to questions about DMPs.

79 *Explanation: the person knows what a DMP is, but did not click the attention check, which*
80 *means the person was not attentive.*

81 (b) if the person does not know what a DMP is (i.e. clicked undecided / I partially disagree / I
82 disagree), this has no consequence.

83 *Explanation: The person does not know what a DMP is, so the person does not need to be*
84 *attentive to this question.*

85 *Comment: For analysis, only persons who know what a DMP is are interesting to consider*
86 *here.*

87 (iv) If at least two attention checks are missed (1st & 2nd, 1st & 3rd, or 2nd & 3rd), the whole
88 data set is deleted.

89 *Explanation: the person is generally not attentive, and is therefore excluded.*

90 (v) If only one category is chosen for all blocks of questions at least 3 times or more (only: I
91 agree / I partially agree / undecided / I rather disagree / I fully disagree), the person is
92 excluded.

93 *Explanation: the person was not attentive enough, and is therefore excluded.*

94

95

96 **Rules for exclusion criteria regarding whole pages of the online questionnaire:**

97 Page 8: If the person is not doing image analysis and processing, the answers on pages 9
98 and 10 are deleted.

99 *Explanation: This is a technical failure of the survey logic: the person should not have seen*
100 *pages 9 and 10.*

101 Page 11: If always the same answer was given on page 11, the answers on page 11 are
102 excluded.

103 *Explanation: non-attentive clicking.*

104 Page 12:

105 • If no image repository is known, all answers afterwards are allowed to be “undecided”.

106 *Explanation: The person does not know anything about the following questions and is*
107 *probably not able to answer. Hence, this is no non-attentive clicking.*

108 • If at least one image repository is known and there was only one answer given in the
109 following questions, page 12 is completely excluded for this entry

110 *Explanation: non-attentive clicking.*

111 Page 13, question block 1: Always the same answer is accepted. No deletions.

112 *Explanation: It may be plausible that all questions are checked with the same answer.*

113 Page 13, questions block 2: If only one answer is checked, the answers on page 13, block 2
114 are excluded for this entry.

115 *Explanation: not-attentive clicking.*

116 Page 15, questions block 1: If only one answer is checked, the answers on page 15, block 1
117 are excluded for this entry.

118 *Explanation: not-attentive clicking.*

119 *Page 16, question block 1:* If only one answer is checked, the answers on page 16, block 1
120 are excluded from this entry.

121 *Explanation: non-attentive clicking.*

122 *Page 16, question block 2:* If only one answer is checked, the answers on page 16, block 2
123 are excluded from this entry.

124 *Explanation: non-attentive clicking.*

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128 **Proceed with Data Analysis**

129 **Subgroups of interest - sheets 5-15** (sheet 4 “groups compare” was used to prepare
130 figures only):

131 “A PhD-undergrad”: Career-level group PhD students and undergraduate students

132 “B PostDoc-PermRes”: Career-level group postdoctoral researchers and permanent
133 research staff

134 “C Group-Leaders”: Career-level group junior and senior group leaders/professors

135 “D Res support”: Career-level group research support and facility staff

136 “Analys-begin”: All entries stating “completely unexperienced” or “beginner” in
137 Q10-7

138 “Analys-pros”: All entries stating “highly qualified expert” or “skilled
139 professional” in Q10-7

140 “DMP_subgroup”: All participants, who stated in Q16.4 Statement 1: “I fully agree”
141 or “I partially agree”

142 The revised version (after peer-review) contains additional sheets to reveal the data included
143 in Supp. Fig. 9b to analyze the answers from respondents who stated to know what a DMP is
144 per career-level group.

145 “DMP-sub A PhD”

146 “DMP-sub B Post”

147 “DMP-sub C Jun-Sen”

148 “DMP-sub D ResSupp”

149

150 The data incl. QC-checks and subgroup analysis is available as Extended Data 4

151 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504713>).

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153 **Free-text comments**

154 **Q16-5: To benefit my own research, this research data management topic is the most pressing**
 155 **issue that needs to be solved:**

- 156 • uniformly DMPs for each institute or working group and how to establish them
- 157 • Get an easy to use system that is clearly structured and adapted to the needs of phytopathology.
 158 Get a detailed introduction into the system and how to use it in my daily work.
- 159 The system should be easily integratable into the day-to-day routine and not add a lot of
 160 additional documentation.
- 161 • Long term data storage -> where? Server? Hard Drives?
- 162 • Simplify sharing data and meta data
- 163 • Databases like OMERO must accept original data formats (lif, czi) and also support analysis
 164 types like Imaris files (including e.g. their surface segmentations).
- 165 • Time-resolved data should be possible to deposit not only as the FLIM-image as tif but also keep
 166 the original ptu or spc file format, else re-analysis is impossible.
- 167 • legal issues, technical implementation, convincing users and, above all, maintenance
- 168 • getting started, changing habits
- 169 • Addition of the metadata (excluding annotations) before data acquisition, by coupling with
 170 electronic notebook or booking system (ex agenda).
- 171 • Open formats. Most microscope manufacturers do not provide open data format for easy access
 172 to image and meta data. A integrated Electronic notebook, image data management and other
 173 data management platforms will help to solve all the above for biologists and researchers
- 174 • what is it about and what is it good for
- 175 • long term storage and personnel-independent annotation.
- 176 • There is a wide choice of ELNs and no consistency - which is one reason why we haven't
 177 implemented them. A community effort to sift through available options and recommend would be
 178 good, especially an ELN that seamlessly collects appropriate metadata when imaging. Currently,
 179 only written notebooks are good enough for this, in my opinion.
- 180 • ELN options
- 181 • How to organizing digital files in a useful, retrievable manner. How to organize files connected to
 182 various projects and or methods to make connections logical.
- 183 • Spread the information about what it is :-)
- 184 • Establish universal standards, vocabulary and definitions, and make education free and easily
 185 available to everyone.
- 186 • More information should be released through different Societies and perform open workshops to
 187 everybody.
- 188 • Imaging data management
- 189 • DMPs at the university level feel as though they do not have collaboration in mind. they feel
 190 restrictive and are mostly ignored in long term collaborations. Thinning out the verbiage and
 191 clearing the red tape from what is allowable and not would make things much more clear and
 192 easier to follow.
- 193 • Specifications for metadata, tools, workflows. Support from funding agencies to
 194 develop metadata collection tools, specifications, workflows. Support from funding agencies for
 195 Data Management Platforms implementation, use, image analysis integration, and maintenance.
 196 Support from institutions/shift in culture for all of above
- 197 • Ease and efficiency of implementation. Insufficient time and staffing to generate ever new
 198 requirements while not draining resources paralysing creative research.
- 199 • lack of teaching data management (along with data analysis) to students.
- 200 • Make it easy to add annotations/metadata to a file directly while imaging. Ideally have
 201 microscope software incorporate the addition of metadata to files.

- 202 • Scripts that extract the time- and amplitude- data from the recorded data files. I could probably do
203 this myself by writing some Matlab code, but it would likely take a week or so since I am not that
204 good at Matlab, so I never get around to do it.
- 205 • It needs to be less time consuming. The institution should provide proper tools and software to
206 support this.
- 207 • Standardisation of image file formats and meta data.
- 208 • The size of the images are huge and sometimes it is impossible to send images via email. Very
209 good computers are needed for image processing

210

211 **Page 18: Do you wish to leave a personal comment?**212 **(Please do not include any information allowing personal identification of yourself or third**
213 **persons!)**

214

- 215 • Well done on a very well structured survey!
- 216 • Thank you for the survey. Hope it helps us understand our needs better.
- 217 • We are desperately looking for an easy to use, standardized system, that can be applied to our
218 research. At the moment, TB of data are stored uselessly on external hard drives and the amount
219 is increasing.
- 220 • I realized that I am obviously not an expert in this field since many of the terms are new for me.
- 221 • Well done survey may be a little bit to lengthy after all, but that always happens when putting
222 together a good survey!
- 223 • Fantastic Project with an urgent need in the community
- 224 • Good luck!
- 225 • I didn't know many of the opportunities, so more information would be very important, I think.
- 226 • I am a facility staff, my work involves mainly collaborative projects in which data stewardship
227 rests typically with my collaborators. My own projects are of smaller scale and technical nature,
228 with much less data produced than in the collaborative projects.
- 229 • Not as geared to a core facility manager who does not have a research program. Thanks for
230 asking important questions.
- 231 • More information should be released through different Societies and perform open workshops to
232 everybody. I wouldn't mind participating as a member.
- 233 • We are in the process of setting up a new core facility for imaging. I would be very interested in
234 the outcome of this poll!
- 235 • Benefit and implementation of data management tools like Omero are still not easy to
236 communicate with scientific stuff. Especially many data analysis tools are not implemented in
237 Omero so it is often only a storage server for data where upload and download is necessary to
238 work with your data. This is for most people an unnecessary extra step for data handling.
239 Databases definitely need improvement in this regard.
- 240 • I really like the idea of electronic lab books and would like to work with them.
- 241 • Greater university technical support for data storage and metadata is essential for widespread
242 adoption of good practices. Trying to implement good data management at my university requires
243 me to work around our IT services more often than with them (with their knowledge/'support'; of
244 this workaround since they don't want to dedicate resources to implementing them, even though
245 the request comes from multiple groups).
- 246 • Thanks for your efforts!

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249 **Survey Logic**

Conditional survey logic scheme of the

2021 NFDI4BIOIMAGE Community Survey

251 **Supplementary Figures****Which discipline describes your work / research best?**

Undergraduate and PhD students

Postdoctoral researchers and permanent research staff

Junior and senior group leaders / professors

Research Support and Facility Staff

Suppl. Fig. 1: Research disciplines of the survey respondents. Up to three items could be selected. All groups were asked to state up to three disciplines (upper bar chart); free-text was offered, too, as one possible choice. Answers included: cell biology (5 x), food research (2 x), ageing research (2 x), systems biology, vascular biology, stem cell biology, virology, bioconjugate chemistry, chemistry, imaging scientist, microscope development, agriculture, and food research.

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Please state if your work includes the following method(s):

Suppl. Fig. 2: Method knowledge and use by the survey respondents. The charts show the relative fraction of each answer per preselected method in each group. Numbers in bars indicate the absolute answers.

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a) Imagine you had to choose ONE method as the single most important method, which one is it?

b) Why did you declare that technique as single most important?

c) How much time on average do you spend on the technique, including all steps you are involved in?

Suppl. Fig. 3: Choices for the most important method by survey participants (upper panel) and reasons to declare this technique as most important (multiple answers possible, middle panel). The lower panel shows the distribution of average work time spent on the most important technique.

256 **When you plan using a new bioimaging technique or instrument, which information source do you use?**

Undergraduate and PhD students

Postdoctoral researchers and permanent research staff

Junior and senior group leaders / professors

Research Support and Facility Staff

Suppl. Fig. 4: Mode of self-performed image analysis. A comparison between the four analyzed groups is shown.

257

a) Does your research involve image processing and (quantitative) image analysis?

b) Which software do you use?

c) Do you use web-applications for image analysis?

d) I know well which image analysis methods exist and what they are used for

e) Which software do you use?

f) Which discipline describes your work best?

Suppl. Fig. 5: Image analysis software use. a) Respondents were asked to state if and how they use bioimage analysis. b) Autonomous image analysis software use by participants. c) Use of web-applications for image analysis. d, e, f) Answers to survey questions from respondents who self-reported as “highly qualified expert” or “skilled professional” (red) and respondents who self-reported as “completely unexperienced” or “beginner” (blue) compared.

Suppl. Fig. 6: External bioimage analysis performed by a collaboration partner of the respondents. Shown are the answers of survey respondents who did not perform bioimage analysis on their own, and from respondents who rely on external analysis to a significant extent in addition to autonomous image analysis.

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Suppl. Fig. 7: Opinion of the respondents on statements about data management platforms. Shown are the relative answer fractions per item in each group (Undergraduate and PhD student, n = 53; Postdoctoral and permanent researchers, n = 65; Junior and senior group leaders, n = 26, Research support and facility staff, n = 48).

260

a) Besides metadata saved automatically by imaging instruments, it is often required to annotate additional metadata for a study. In a typical bioimaging experiment, do you collect additional metadata and how?

b) In which format or structure do you annotate additional metadata?

Suppl. Fig. 8: Details on metadata collection by participants and formats of annotation.

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a) What is your opinion on these statements about Data Management Plans (DMPs)? (all respondents)

b) What is your opinion on these statements about Data Management Plans (DMPs)? (per career level group)

Suppl. Fig. 9: Respondents' opinions on statements about DMPs. a) The answers for eight statements are shown for those respondents who stated "I fully agree" or "I partially agree" to the first question (86 respondents). The results are shown as absolute answers per item. b) Relative answers to the same questions as in a, shown for those respondents of each career level subgroup that answered "I fully agree" or "I partially agree" to the first question in a (Undergraduate and PhD students, n=13; Postdoctoral and permanent researchers, n=24; Junior and senior group leaders / professors, n=19; Research support staff, n=28). Note that 2 of the 86 respondents shown in a are not included in the career group level analysis.

What is your opinion on the following statements about electronic lab notebooks (ELNs):

Suppl. Fig. 10: Respondents' answers to nine statements about electronic lab notebooks on a five-item scale. The results are shown as relative fraction of answer items in each subgroup (Undergraduate and PhD students, n=55; Postdoctoral and permanent researchers, n=66; Junior and senior group leaders / professors, n=27; Research support staff, n=50).

Spearman's Correlations

		Community standards
Own, individual standards	n	198
	Spearman's rho	-0.403
	p-value	< .001

Suppl. Fig. 11: Self-reported data handling in accordance with community standards. a) Respondents answers to the indicated statements per group (Undergraduate and PhD students, n=55; Postdoctoral and permanent researchers, n=66; junior and senior group leaders / professors, n=27; Research support staff, n=48). b) Relative fractions of answer-items from all participants on this page who answered both questions (n = 198). Answer items were transformed to an ordinal scale as indicated. Spearman's Correlation was calculated using JASP v 0.16.

a) Think of image data sharing with researchers who are NOT direct collaborators.

What is your opinion on the following statements?

b) What is your opinion on the following statements about image data repositories?

Suppl. Fig. 12: Opinions on data sharing and data reuse (a), and repositories (b) (corresponding to Fig. 8). Respondents answers to the indicated statements per group (undergraduate and PhD students, n=55; Postdoctoral and permanent researchers, n=66; Junior and senior group leaders / professors, n=27; Research support staff, n=48).